

CRUSHING OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES AND PARAMETER IDENTIFICATION FOR MODEL DEVELOPMENT

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1 Introduction

Weight savings in automotive structures are critical to further reduce fuel consumption and meet future emission targets. Due to their high specific material properties C-fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) may offer superior performance compared to their metallic counterparts and may therefore be one way to achieve such weight savings. Crashworthiness is an important driver for vehicle design where CFRP may be used to save weight. However, currently a large number of tests are necessary to design composite structures for energy absorption, which can be both expensive and time consuming. This is due to a lack of robust models and a good understanding of the mechanisms governing energy absorption (Soden et al. [1]). The focus of this work is thus twofold. In a previous study by Engel et al. [2] we presented data for axial impact testing of composite structures. Here, additional data for off-axis testing of composite structures during dynamic impact is presented. In addition, static coupon tests were conducted to determine basic material data such as tensile and compressive strength. The two data sets were then analyzed to identify key parameters that govern energy absorption. The aim is a simple understanding of the geometrical and material parameters affecting energy absorption.

2 Literature Review

It has previously been demonstrated that geometrical features, such as wall-thickness (Bisagni [3]), corner radius (Bambach et al. [4]) and laminate architecture (Mamalis et al. [5], Laananen et al. [6]) can affect energy absorption in composite materials. However, some of the past results are contradictory. Whilst Hamada et al. [7] showed an indirect correlation of

wall-thickness and specific energy absorption, this trend could not be confirmed in Kim et al. [8]. This may be due to the interaction of geometrical or laminate features, which could have been varied inadvertently. These underlying interactions are not yet studied and understood in detail.

In most cases, specimens with circular cross-sections were used for studying energy absorption, e.g. by Kim et al. [8], Brighton et al. [9] and Farley [10]. This was due to relative ease of manufacturing and a smaller number of geometrical parameters, which have to be taken into account. Palanivelu et al. [11] have shown differences in energy absorption for nominally comparable specimens with circular or rectangular cross-section. In addition circular structures for energy absorption have limited relevance for automotive structures. This is due to the different requirements a certain structure has to fulfil. For example a conventional engine carrier is not only the main energy absorbing structure during a frontal crash event, but also the main connector for engine and front axle system to the car structure. Historically, these engine carriers have been rectangular. So there is a lack of knowledge concerning the energy absorption of rectangular composite profiles.

Automotive crash structures may also undergo oblique dynamic loading [12], which has seen only limited research. Previous studies e.g. by Ochelski et al. [13] have only investigated conical structures under non-axial loading. Studies on carriers with a constant cross-section under non-axial dynamic impact are missing.

Automotive structures are basically designed for strength and stiffness. In a second step crash

performance is tested and optimized. Thus, preliminary laminate configurations and geometries are known when vehicle design is optimized for crash. This is why an approach to derive crash performance metrics from laminate properties is needed. These properties can be generated from coupon tests and may allow estimating the energy absorption during early vehicle design. Some earlier studies have already aimed to establish this link. by Hadavinia [14], Beard et al. [15], Solaimurugan et al. [16, 17] already aimed to establish this link, but concentrated on critical energy release rate in delamination mode I (G_I^C).

The present study deals with the influence of geometrical parameters and laminate architecture on crash performance of rectangular profiles. Geometrical features and laminate architecture were varied. Those parameters varied directly, will be called base parameters throughout this paper. The approach of Design of Experiments is applied to reduce the number of necessary tests. The specimens were tested dynamically under angles of 0deg, 10deg and 20deg. The tested parameters were correlated to defined governing variables describing crash performance, describing structural behaviour under dynamic axial loading. Coupon tests were additionally conducted to test the in-plane compression, tensile, and bending strength and stiffness as well as interlaminar shear strength of the laminates. Material data were then correlated to governing variables. Since base parameters are defined from a manufacturing point of view, derived parameters as wall thickness (THK) and structural compressive strength (R_{ax}) are correlated to governing variables to identify physically meaningful interpretations of the parameters tested.

3 Experimental Procedure

3.1 Sample manufacture

Parameters altering geometry and laminate architecture were chosen to study their influence on crash performance of profiles with rectangular cross section. These were corner radius (R), aspect ratio (AR), axial fibre ratio (AFR) and number of braided layers (NLay). For each parameter a high and low

level was defined. The relation between physical variables and normalized test levels is summarised in Tab. 1. For the definition of AR one side length was held constant, the length of the slender side was varied. Relevant dimensions are also included in Tab. 1. The possible combinations of those parameters on the two levels each defined the configuration for the individual specimen. Each configuration was tested twice in the case of axial loading and the data were averaged.

Tab. 1: Sample configurations for dynamic axial impact

Parameter		-	0	+
Corner Radius	[mm]	15	20	25
UD-Volume fraction	[%]	28	44	61
Braided Layers	[-]	2	3	4
Aspect ratio	[-]	1:2.00	1:1.40	1:1.08
Slender side	[mm]	70	100	130
Wide side	[mm]	140	140	140

Specimens were braided on a foam core. SGL 50k rovings were used as filler yarns, 12k and 24k Toho Tenax HTS40 rovings as braiding yarns. Braiding yarns were changed to alter AFR in the desired range. Preforms were wrapped in peel ply and inserted into an aluminium mould. Using low-pressure resin transfer moulding (RTM) the components were infused with resin. Afterwards peel ply and core material was removed before tempering. See Engel et al. [2] for further details.

From this set of configurations an additional subset with a corner radius of 25 mm was generated for non-axial tests and additional specimens were manufactured.

For determination of material data two additional specimens were manufactured. For AR, R and NLay the reference level (Tab. 1, Level „0“) was chosen. One specimen was manufactured with AFR = 28% (“Low” Level) another one with 60% (“High” level). Material testing was then performed quasi-statically, considering the respective standards as far as possible, see Tab. 2 for details.

The nomenclature of relevant faces of the profile and directions is shown in Fig. 1. Due to constraints arising from the geometry tensile tests could not be

performed in transverse direction. The coupons for tension testing would have been too short to apply enough clamping length, while ensuring undisturbed straining in the relevant area of the coupon. Further, ILSS tests were only conducted in axial direction. Coupon dimensions are summarised in Tab. 2. Each test was repeated five times and then averaged to improve statistical relevance.

Fig. 1: Naming convention of faces and directions in studied structure

3.2 Testing procedure

For dynamic impact testing each profile specimen was glued into a grooved base plate. The base plate was then mounted into the test rig (Fig. 2). The impactor mass was varied depending on the expected energy absorption to ensure a reasonable crash length. Thus a stable fracturing could be reached. The initial impactor speed was held constant at 8.2 m/s. For each test the impactor was accelerated to the desired speed. The specimen then absorbed the kinetic energy imparted by the impactor, see Fig. 3.

During testing the acceleration at the base plate and the displacement of the impactor were recorded as a function of time. High-speed imaging was used to capture the onset and propagation of failure during the impact event. Further, post-test inspection was

used to correlate the measured force-time curve to specific failure modes.

Side View – Overview Test Rig

- 1 – pressure chamber
 - 2 – variable mass
 - 3 – impact plate
 - 4 – specimen
 - 5 – base plate
- screwed to test rig

Top View – Canted Impactor

Fig. 2: Schematically drawing of crash test rig

For off-axis testing specimen were mounted identically to axial testing. The impactor was then slanted at the desired angle to realize the off-axis impact, see bottom of Fig. 2. Impactor velocity was held constant at 8.2 m/s. Mass of the impactor was varied as for axial load case.

Tab. 2: Overview material data tests

	Loadcase	Standard	Specimens* dimension	
Axial	Slender	Tension	DIN EN 2561	100 x 15 mm
		Compression	DIN 14126	100 x 15 mm
		3PB	DIN EN ISO 14125	100 x 15 mm
		ILSS	DIN EN ISO 14130	40 x 20 mm
	Wide	Tension	DIN EN 2561	100 x 15 mm
		Compression	DIN 14126	100 x 15 mm
		3PB	DIN EN ISO 14125	100 x 15 mm
		ILSS	DIN EN ISO 14130	40 x 20 mm
Transverse	Slender	Compression	DIN 14126	60 x 15 mm
		3PB	DIN EN ISO 14125	60 x 10 mm
	Wide	Compression	DIN 14126	100 x 15 mm
		3PB	DIN EN ISO 14125	100 x 15 mm

Fig. 3: Example of a braided carbon composite structure a) prior to testing and b) after testing (Engel et al. [2])

3.3 Statistical Analysis

Response Surface Methodology (RSM, see Myers et al. [18] for details), designates a set of tools for studying a physical system by means of statistical analysis. Therefore a set of independent parameters x , such as corner radius (R) or side lengths' ratio (AR), was correlated linearly to the governing variables y , which were mean crushing force (FMean) and peak load (FPeak). The quality of each model was tested using R_{adj}^2 , which is defined as shown in (Eq. 1).

$$R_{adj}^2 = 1 - \frac{n-1}{n-p} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \bar{y}_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^2}{n}}{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^2}{n}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where n is the number of observations, p the number of parameters included in the model. y_i and \bar{y}_i is the response measured and the response predicted for the i -th variation, respectively.

The significance of the individual parameters was tested by calculating its t -value according to Eq. 2

$$t_0 = \frac{b_j}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 [(X'X)^{-1}]_{jj}}} \quad (2)$$

with b_j the j -th coefficient, σ^2 the standard deviation of the model, X the matrix of parameters x and 'jj' marking the diagonal element corresponding to the tested parameter. The t_0 -value is then compared to the student's t -distribution for a confidence interval of 95%. If t_0 is larger than a critical value $t_{0.025, n-p-1}$, then the coefficient is significant.

To make sure that the linear approach was justified, a test for Lack of Fit (LOF) was performed for axial load case in accordance to Eq. 3.

$$F_0 = \frac{SS_{LOF}/m-p}{SS_{PE}/n-m} \quad (3)$$

$$SS_{LOF} = \sum_{i=1}^m n_i (\bar{y}_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

$$SS_{PE} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (y_{ij} - \bar{y}_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

Where m is the number of tested levels and \hat{y} the mean response on the j -th level. It was assumed that F_0 -Value is distributed as F -Statistic, with a critical value $F_{0.05, m-p, n-m}$. If the calculated F_0 -Value is smaller than the critical value, than the linear assumption is valid.

4 Experimental Results

4.1 Quasi-static tests

An overview of the static test results is given in Tab. 3 for the slender side and in Tab. 4 for the wide side. Comparing the results for coupons cut from either slender or wide side of the profil it can be seen, that the mechanical properties vary. This is due to different fibre orientation during braiding process where the fibre angle changes when layup-path deviate from a geodesic line (see Fig. 4).

Deviation in repeated tests is varying with load case and specimen configuration and takes values between 3 and 35%. Tests with high fibre content in loaded direction show smaller Coefficients of Variance (CoV). Highest CoV appear under compressive loading. For future material testing specifically in braided structures a higher number of tests, especially in transverse direction und under compressive loading should be chosen.

4.2 Dynamic tests

An overview of the specimen data for axial testing together with the measured values for peak load (FPeak), mean crushing force (FMean), specific energy absorption (SEA) and crush force efficiency (CFE) is summarised Tab. 5.

Tab. 3: Material data determined from coupon-tests, slender side

		LC		slender side					
		Stress	Std	CoV	Stiffness	Std	CoV		
		[MPa]	Dev		[MPa]	Dev			
Axial	28%	Tens	350	61	17%	20571	2496	12%	
		Comp	223	34	15%	9847	1114	11%	
		3PB	345	57	17%	26366	3788	14%	
		ILSS	34	1	3%	-	-	-	
	60%	Tens	643	26	4%	33058	1751	5%	
		Comp	249	16	6%	13342	708	5%	
		3PB	576	31	5%	43508	6416	15%	
		ILSS	45	4	9%	-	-	-	
	Transverse	28%	Tens	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Comp	105	13	12%	4644	176	4%
3PB			159	16	10%	8872	405	5%	
60%		Tens	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		Comp	86	24	28%	3914	758	19%	
		3PB	102	14	13%	5988	981	16%	

Tab. 4: Material data determined from coupon-tests, wide side

		LC		wide side					
		Stress	Std	CoV	Stiffness	Std	CoV		
		[MPa]	Dev		[MPa]	Dev			
Axial	28%	Tens	220	25	11%	19087	2036	11%	
		Comp	188	17	9%	9296	1027	11%	
		3PB	258	32	12%	16842	5637	33%	
		ILSS	30	4	13%	-	-	-	
	60%	Tens	572	88	15%	28807	3225	11%	
		Comp	225	79	35%	12087	1691	14%	
		3PB	462	56	12%	29538	4657	16%	
		ILSS	42	3	7%	-	-	-	
	Transverse	28%	Tens	138	19	14%	11765	1163	10%
			Comp	118	4	3%	5786	611	11%
3PB			200	20	10%	11537	1334	12%	
60%		Tens	82	8	10%	9151	791	9%	
		Comp	70	13	18%	5266	1117	21%	
		3PB	156	11	7%	8224	804	10%	

The repeated tests for every configuration are labelled with roman numerals I and II. All specimens showed identical fracture mode, which was splaying, according to the notation of Farley et al. [19].

For the axial load case SEA values ranged from 21 to 41 kJ/kg and CFE reached values between 27 and 48%. Repeatability was high, and consequently the Coefficients of Variance (CoV) were well below 10% in all configurations under axial loading.

Fig. 4: Scheme showing deviation of fibre directions due to profil's geometry

Both SEA and CFE are relatively low compared to other studies, however this may be explained by the rectangular cross-section and thick braid layers (Thornton et al. [20], Mamalis et al. [21],[22]).

Fig. 5: SEA for non-axial impact under 10 and 20 deg normalised to values of axial tests

Off-Axis data is summarised in (Tab. 6). Comparing the data from axial tests and tests with 10 deg impact angle shows only small changes in SEA. However, SEA decreases with further increase of impact angle to 20 deg by 13% on average (Fig. 5). This drop is due to the asymmetric delamination in splaying mode, producing a relatively thin and a thicker frond. Whilst the thinner part of the wall is failing, the thicker one undergoes mostly elastic deformation, absorbing less energy. The effect becomes stronger with increasing impact angle as shown by Mamalis et al. [23].

Tab. 5: Experimental results for axial dynamic test

	R	Nlay	AFR	ALPH	AR	THK		FPeak		FMean		SEA		CFE	
						[mm]		[kN]		[kN]		[kJ/kg]		[-]	
						I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II
V01	15	2	28%	0	2.00	2.90	2.70	142	135	39	37	34	26	0.41	0.39
V02	25	2	28%	0	2.00	2.80	2.80	139	133	41	41	28	29	0.42	0.43
V03	15	2	60%	0	2.00	2.50	2.30	171	151	41	37	32	30	0.35	0.32
V04	25	2	60%	0	2.00	2.60	2.60	173	155	48	44	36	35	0.39	0.36
V05	15	4	28%	0	2.00	5.40	5.30	268	256	83	86	29	31	0.40	0.43
V06	25	4	28%	0	2.00	5.50	5.40	262	272	89	86	32	31	0.44	0.42
V07	15	4	60%	0	2.00	4.60	4.60	332	348	93	89	37	36	0.41	0.38
V08	25	4	60%	0	2.00	4.90	4.90	333	371	104	100	41	41	0.43	0.42
V09	15	2	28%	0	1.08	2.70	2.60	228	170	42	38	23	21	0.31	0.29
V10	25	2	28%	0	1.08	2.80	3.00	195	207	43	46	23	25	0.31	0.31
V11	15	2	60%	0	1.08	2.40	2.50	230	209	41	43	25	26	0.27	0.31
V12	25	2	60%	0	1.08	2.70	2.70	233	261	57	54	24	32	0.35	0.35
V13	15	4	28%	0	1.08	5.60	5.40	414	414	110	116	30	32	0.39	0.41
V14	25	4	28%	0	1.08	5.50	5.50	414	414	118	120	32	33	0.43	0.42
V15	15	4	60%	0	1.08	4.80	4.70	412	414	135	123	40	37	0.48	0.38
V16	25	4	60%	0	1.08	4.80	4.90	414	414	127	120	38	36	0.42	0.40

Tab. 6: Experimental results for axial dynamic test

	R	Nlay	AFR	ALPH	AR	THK	FPeak	FMean	SEA	CFE
V02aI	25	2	28%	10	2.00	3.10	57	43	29	0.76
V02aII	25	2	28%	20	2.00	3.00	51	34	24	0.67
V04bI	25	2	60%	10	2.00	2.50	71	44	33	0.62
V04aII	25	2	60%	20	2.00	2.60	44	30	24	0.68
V06aI	25	4	28%	10	2.00	5.40	111	81	29	0.73
V06aII	25	4	28%	20	2.00	5.30	113	89	32	0.78
V08bI	25	4	60%	10	2.00	4.80	144	109	44	0.76
V08bII	25	4	60%	20	2.00	4.80	129	97	38	0.76
V10aI	25	2	28%	10	1.08	3.00	69	48	26	0.70
V10aII	25	2	28%	20	1.08	2.90	59	39	21	0.66
V12aI	25	2	60%	10	1.08	2.70	70	46	26	0.65
V12aII	25	2	60%	20	1.08	2.60	61	35	20	0.58
V14aI	25	4	28%	10	1.08	5.50	156	111	30	0.71
V14bII	25	4	28%	20	1.08	5.50	149	111	30	0.75
V16bI	25	4	60%	10	1.08	4.80	144	112	34	0.78
V16bII	25	4	60%	20	1.08	4.70	134	94	29	0.70

Due to highly localized stresses at the beginning of deformation, the peak load drops and therefore CFE increases under off-axial loading (Fig. 6). The effect is obvious for loading under 10 deg in comparison with axial results. It does not become significantly higher for higher loading angles of 20 deg.

Fig. 6: CFE for non-axial impact under 10 and 20 deg normalised to values of axial tests

5 Parameter identification

5.1 Axial Impact

To develop an understanding of the effect of base parameters (R, AR, AFR and N Lay) on crash performance a first-order model containing interaction terms was fitted to the experimental data see Eq. 6.

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j x_j + \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^k \beta_{ij} x_i x_j \quad (6)$$

Herein y are the predicted responses, x are the parameters, β_j are the fitted coefficients and i, j, k are index variables. All calculations were performed with parameters standardized to [-1;1]. This enables direct comparison of the parameters' effects on the governing variable. Response variables were mean force and peak load. This was done since in automotive design the forces are much more common in evaluation of crash performance than the

derived measures. Furthermore the interpretation of those primary results avoids unnecessary complexity compared to deduced parameters as SEA or CFE.

Quality measures for all analysed configurations are summarised in Tab. 7. T-statistics and normalised coefficients for FMean and FPeak model in base configuration are shown in Fig. 7.

Tab. 7: Quality measures R^2_{adj} and F0 lack of fit for all discussed configurations, axial and non-axial loadcase

		FPeak		FMean	
		R ² adj	F0 LOF	R ² adj	F0 LOF
Axial	Base	99%	0.79	98%	3.71
	THK vs. N Lay	97%	2.36	97%	6.33
	Rax vs. AFR	98%	0.70	98%	2.58
	TD vs. AR	98%	2.06	98%	2.96
		FPeak		FMean	
		R ² adj	F0 LOF	R ² adj	F0 LOF
Non-Axial	Base	88%	32.99	94%	3.29
	THK vs. N Lay	90%	47.65	97%	1.74
	Rax vs. AFR	90%	47.60	97%	1.66
	TD vs. AR	90%	47.12	98%	1.48

The chosen linear approach is valid for the model describing FPeak, but not for FMean.

It is obvious that out of the base parameters N Lay, AR and AFR are significantly influencing FPeak as well as FMean. R is only marginally influencing the loads in the parameter range tested. Moreover the interaction term AR x THK is significant. This corresponds to results of previous studies by Farley [24] and Palanivelu et al. [11], where interactions were shown between wall thickness and structures dimension. This interaction is mostly described as t/D-ratio.

Varying the number of braided layers alters three main properties of the structure. Those are wall thickness, relative thickness of single layer with respect to wall thickness and the number and distribution of regions sensitive to interlaminar failure. Substituting N Lay by THK in the model and analysing the resulting t-statistic and coefficients, it can be seen that neither ratios between coefficients, nor significances are changed (Fig. 8). Thus it can be

concluded that in the present study the main effect is the alteration of wall thickness (THK).

Where a and b are the side lengths of the profile, U its circumference and σ_c^s and σ_c^w the compressive strengths of the slender and wide side, respectively.

Fig. 7: T-statistic and coefficients for base-configuration, axial loading

It is known, that the axial fibre fraction alters compressive strength and stiffness of a laminate. So AFR is compared to compressive strength of the laminate gained from coupon tests. As discussed the laminate properties vary with the face of the profile from which the coupon has been taken. That is why an estimate of effective compression strength of the structure was calculated (R_{ax}). It is based on the assumption that the individual faces of the profile behave like parallel springs with different stiffness and strength, respectively. R_{ax} is thus calculated by Eq. 7.

$$R_{ax}^- = \frac{a - 2R}{U} \sigma_c^s + \frac{b - 2R}{U} \sigma_c^w + \frac{2\pi R}{U} \cdot \frac{\sigma_c^s + \sigma_c^w}{2} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 8: T-statistic and coefficients for THK vs. Nlay configuration, axial loading

Incorporating R_{ax} in the model by substituting AFR t-statistic and coefficients are resulting as shown in Fig. 9. Whilst the significant parameters of the previous analyses are the same, an additional interaction term – $THK \times R_{ax}^-$ becomes relevant. This term can be interpreted as a scaling of strength measured on coupons with $N_{lay} = 3$ to the wall thickness of each specimen. It must be taken into account that parameters are correlated to a force while R_{ax}^- is a strength, see Eq. 8.

$$R_{ax}^- = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{F}{t \cdot U} \rightarrow \frac{F}{U} = R_{ax}^- \cdot t \quad (8)$$

Fig. 9: T-Statistic and coefficients for Rax vs. AFR configuration, axial loading

A measure which is often studied due to its known influence on specific energy absorption is the ratio of wall-thickness and cross-sectional dimension, t/D -ratio (TD). In the present study TD is defined as the ratio of wall-thickness and the smaller of the two side-lengths. Essentially, TD relates the strength and stability of the laminate to the overall dimensions. Due to the fact that a chamfered trigger is used and no stability failure occurred during tests, a correlation between TD and FPeak could not be estimated. Based on the strong correlation found in other studies between TD and SEA a visible effect between TD and FMean would be expected. Statistical correlation shows that this assumption is true in terms of FPeak. TD is not a significant parameter in contrast to the substituted AR. For the FMean-model TD does not provide additional information to the studied parameter combination

compared to AR, leading to a nearly unchanged model (see Fig. 10).

Fig. 10: T-Statistic and coefficients for TD x AR configuration, axial loading

5.2 Non-Axial Impact

In all non-axial test configurations model quality in terms of R^2_{adj} values was below values reached for axial loading. This is especially true for FPeak models. This suggests that there is generally a greater part of unexplained variance in the model.

Since R was held constant and the loading angle (ALPH) was introduced to the model, base configuration changes. Base parameters are AR, ALPH, NLay and AFR. Fitting to this Configuration leads to differing significant parameters for FMean and FPeak (Fig. 11) compared to axial loading data. FPeak depends on all the four base parameters and the interaction term ALPH x NLay. FMean is a function of AR, ALPH and NLay only. As in the

axial load case, NLay influences both command variables strongly, but for FPeak ALPH is even more effective. This is due to localized stresses under non-axial loading, decreasing FPeak.

Fig. 11: T-Statistic and coefficients for base-configuration, non-axial loading

It has been discussed for axial load case, that the change of NLay influences not only wall thickness, but also the number of weak points in a laminate and the relative thickness of a single layer in comparison to wall thickness. This can be shown when substituting NLay by THK (Fig. 12). The models remain the same in the axial load case, in off-axis testing both models change. For FPeak the interaction term ALPH x THK is insignificant, suggesting that the corresponding interaction term ALPH x NLay provides more information than only the variation of wall thickness. The FMean model is

complemented by AFR, AR x THK and THK x AFR. So the complexity of the model increases, without improving model quality significantly. That is to say that variance due to NLay is not fully captured by variance of THK.

In contrast substituting AFR by Rax does not change the models for FPeak or FMean, so in this case the AFR is also capturing the compressive strength of the structure, as has been stated for the axial load case.

Substituting TD by AR has no influence on significance and effect of base parameters, but leads to changes of significant interaction terms in the case of FMean. All interaction terms including TD became significant, whilst THK x Rax becomes insignificant. Base parameters of FPeak are not changed, but interaction terms TD x ALPH and ALPH x THK became significant.

Fig. 12: T-Statistic and coefficients for THK vs. NLay configuration, non-axial loading

6 Summary

Braided CFRP profiles with rectangular cross-section were tested under dynamic axial and non-axial loading. Furthermore, mechanical material properties for the braided profiles under in-plane tension and compression, as well as 3-Point bending and interlaminar shear were determined from quasi-static coupon tests. The influence of geometrical parameters, as well as the mechanical material data on crash performance was then studied. Due to the high aspect ratio of the investigated geometries fibre angles varied for slender and wide side. Consequently mechanical properties of the slender side of the profile were generally higher than those on the wide side. The change in properties was due to the braiding yarns, which shifted to lower angles on the slender side with respect to axial direction.

The influence of these mechanical properties as well as geometric variables on crash performance of profiles under axial loading was then studied. Different structural properties were varied with the number of braided layers. Those were the wall thickness, the relative thickness of a ply with respect to wall-thickness and the number of regions prone to delamination. Out of those three it could be shown that in the present study the wall thickness covered the same variance as the number of braided layers. Further, it was found that changing the axial fibre ratio has the same effect on mean crushing force and peak load as on change of axial compressive strength. The t/D-ratio, here defined as wall-thickness to slender side of the profile, corresponded to the aspect ratio for the mean load, however correlation with peak load was poor. In addition interaction terms aspect ratio x wall-thickness and wall-thickness x compressive strength of the profile became significant. This suggests that t/D provides less information on the variance of data than aspect ratio.

SEA and CFE changed for loading under 10deg and 20deg. Whilst under non-axial loading with an angle of 10 deg the SEA was nearly the same as in axial load case, it dropped by 13% when impact angle increases to 20 deg. Concerning CFE an increase when loading under 10 deg instead of 0 deg was

found, but there was no further improvement for higher impact angles. The increase of CFE may have resulted from highly localized stresses at the beginning of deformation under non-axial loading.

Statistical analyses of non-axial tests showed significant changes in analytical models compared to axial models. In particular the effect of the number of braided layers was found to be different. Whilst under axial loading this parameter was interchangeably with the wall thickness, this was not the case under non-axial loading. This suggests that additional effect may influence off-axis impact, however, due to a limited database this could not be clarified. Further studies should aim to study this in more detail, for example by varying number of layers in a wider range. Further, interactions between variables should be the object of further investigations. The goal should be the ability to predict SEA and failure mode using laminate properties and profiles geometry only to enable analytical optimization of such structures in an early design phase.

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